

Impact of Job Satisfaction on Employee's Performance: Empirical Evidence from Ghana Health Service

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Abstract

The Ghana Health Service is working to build a happy work force to run the organization's well-being. In fact, if an employee feels happy with the work, then an employee is motivated to put more effort into results. Employees of the hospitals of the Ghana Health Service can accomplish the requirements of job satisfaction by taking. There have been numerous strikes by Doctors, Nurses, Health Assistants in Ghana since they were dissatisfied with pay, promotion, working conditions, development policies, care given to doctors and many other factors. These have warranted the need to examine the effects of the determinants of Job satisfaction on employee performance using Teaching Hospitals in Ghana.

The sample comprise 300 respondents from selected teaching Hospitals in Ghana. The research analysed the data with statistical package for social science (SPSS), descriptive and statistical regression model with the use of structured questionnaires. The research finds positive relationship between Employee performance and the determinants to Job satisfaction. This implies that, employees' compensation and benefits, working conditions, Job safety and security, promotion, and relationship with supervisors, and workers are positively related with employee's performance and the effect is statistically significant. Therefore, in order to enhance the employee performance in the teaching Hospitals in Ghana, the government should focus on all determinants of job satisfaction and not only on any one of these factors. In addition, management of the company should provide good working conditions for its employees, so as to boost their morale. Certain policy recommendations were discussed.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance, Hospitals, Working Conditions, Ghana.

Introduction

People are an integral part of organizational success. Depending on how well people are integrated into the management process, they can affect organizational performance or other aspects. To understand the critical importance of people in an organization, one must recognize that human factors are synonymous with organization. A well-managed organization often sees ordinary employees as a fundamental source of quality and productivity improvement. Such organizations do not invest capital, but instead use employees as a fundamental source of improvement.

In a competitive and unpredictable environment, organizations try to maintain and enhance their competitive advantage. Many industries operate in such an environment, and employees play an important role in the exchange of products and services (Meng, & Berger, 2019). In a service organization, employees have a significant impact on organizational performance. According to the new public management principles, all public sector organizations should be entrepreneurial and provide high quality services. The organization has a strong desire for employee job satisfaction (Osagbemi, 2013).

The Ghana Health Service tries to create a satisfied work force to operate the well-being of the organization. In fact, when an employee feels satisfaction about the job, an employee is motivated to put greater effort to the performance. The imperatives of job satisfaction can be achieved by taking employees of Hospitals of the Ghana Health Service. There have been numerous strikes by Doctors, Nurses, Health Assistants in Ghana since they were dissatisfied with pay, promotion, working conditions, development policies, care given to doctors and many other factors. For example, 60 percent of health workers been out of action would have a great impact on a country as death rate escalates (Kazmi, 2011). It shows that satisfying employees is one of the most important functions of management. With this, the current research examines the factors of job satisfaction and its impacts of employee's job performance. This study contributes to the literature in

diverse ways. Others have looked at the impact of job satisfaction on job performance of employees in Ghana.

The review of literature suggests that there are researches that have been carried out mostly from USA, Malaysia, UK, Ghana, Iran, India, Nigeria, etc on this same subject but none has examined from the health sectors. Most literature used one corporate organization's such banks, district assembly, schools, manufacturing companies in assessing the factors or determinants of job satisfaction affecting job performance.

Nonetheless, the health sector is very diverse and consists of a wide variety of people, from different age groups to specialized staff. The health service has to achieve a sector-wide goal of providing health services that meet the needs of the general public, but numerous factors or numerous of job satisfaction affecting employee's performance have been overlooked. In addition, even though, few studies have examined on this same subject but none examined the determinants of job satisfaction implying Job satisfaction acting as mediating variable.

Therefore, research scholars believed that, assessing the determinants of job satisfaction affecting employee's performance of Health workers of four (4) teaching hospitals in Ghana would be significant, hence the study contributed towards filling this gap. The rest of the manuscript is as follows: the next section is the related literature review and hypothesis development, the next is research methodology, followed by results and finding and the final section is conclusions and recommendations.

Literature Review

Job satisfaction is a happy or positive emotional state that results from an assessment of one's work or work experience. This means that satisfied employees have a positive attitude towards work, resulting in high levels of performance, and unsatisfactory employees have a negative attitude towards work, resulting in low performance results. On the other hand, job performance includes obvious behaviours that people observe at work that are important to achieving organizational goals that must be relevant to the organization's goals (Rotundo and Sackett, 2002).

Emerging organizational behavioral and organizational psychology literature suggests that job satisfaction and performance relationships are the most studied areas (Judge et al., 2001). The relationship between them has been extensively studied over the past few decades, and the growing interest in research on these two phenomena is unusual. Weiss and Cropanzano (2014) describe the relationship between the Holy Grail for the study of industrial/organizational psychology and the fundamentals behind the rise of interest in the relationship between two variables identified by different organizations in various parts of the world to identify employee satisfaction Proper control (said et al., 2012).

Relationship between job satisfaction and job performance

Hawthorne's research laid the foundation for studying the impact of employee attitudes on performance. After Hawthorne's research, more and more researchers began to critically study the idea that a happier employee is a more efficient employee. Most of their literature reviews suggest that there is a weak and contradictory relationship between job satisfaction and performance. Iaffaldano and Muchinsky (1985) as cited in Robert et al 2020; Adeyemo's (2010) further consulted the literature and proposed that the statistical relationship between job satisfaction and performance is 0.17, indicating that there is a certain correlation between job satisfaction and performance. They further claimed that the relationship between the above two variables is the result of "management boom" and "illusion". This result supports the views of researchers and organizations, managers, and HR practitioners who believe that the relationship between job satisfaction and performance is not important.

Further research disagreed with the findings of Iaffaldano and Muchinsky (2015). Organ (1988) argues that the inability to determine the close relationship between these two variables is due to the narrow definition of performance. Organ (2018) argues that when performance is defined as considering key behaviors that are not normally revealed in performance assessments, such as organizational citizenship behavior, the link between it and job satisfaction improves. According to research by Organ and Ryan (2015), research tends to support the view of Organ (1988) because job satisfaction is related to organizational citizenship behavior. The current in-depth analysis of 301 studies shows that when correlations are accurately corrected, the average correlation between job satisfaction and performance is limited. The performance must be 0.30 (Judge et al., (2001). They attributed the differences in results to the findings of Iaffaldano and Muchinsky (2013) dealing only with aspect-level satisfaction rather than the global level. Since performance is

conceptualized at a general level, it is clear that job satisfaction at the level will automatically produce a lower correlation than measurement satisfaction at the global level. They further found that the correlation between job satisfaction and performance in complex jobs is higher than in less complex jobs.

Empirical Literature Review

A large number of researchers have proved the importance of job satisfaction of employees in business organizations. Job satisfaction is so important in that its absence often leads to lethargy and reduced organizational commitment.

Sometimes workers move from one profession to another that is considered a greener pasture when there is dwindling economy and its concomitant such as poor conditions of service and late payment of salaries (Bowling et al 2015). Explaining its nature some researchers (e.g. Loan, 2020; King, 2017; Robert et al 2020;) tend to agree that job satisfaction is essentially controlled by factors described in Adeyemo's (2010) perspectives as external to the worker. From this new point, satisfaction on a job might be motivated by the nature of the job, its pervasive social climate and extent to which workers peculiar needs are met (Tella, Ayeni & Popoola, 2007).

Sowmya and Panchanathan (2011) analyzed the factors influencing job satisfaction in the banking sector and found that job suitability, working conditions and other employee's interpersonal skills significantly affect the level of job satisfaction. Javid, Balouch & Hassan (2014) analyzed the determinants of job satisfaction and their impact on employee performance and turnover intentions. Job placement environment, job loyalty, and employee empowerment were taken as variables. It was found that there is a positive relationship between these factors and job satisfaction. It was also found that there is a negative relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. Saleem, Majeed & Usman (2013) found that nature of work, job stress, organization strategy and policy, selection and recruitment procedure have a positive impact on the job satisfaction. Hussain and Mujtaba (2013) concluded that HR practices like job autonomy, leadership behaviour and team work have positive relationship with job satisfaction in the microfinance sector in Pakistan.

Research has shown that satisfaction to some extent is based on disposition (Judge & Larsen, Aveh, Dadzie & Krah (2013) concluded that the success of Microfinance banks were influenced by two factors; the staff remunerations and staff turnover. Sattar & Ali (2014) found that leadership behaviour and promotions strongly affect the employee satisfaction. Hira and Waqas (2012) found a positive relationship between employee job satisfaction and employee performance. The increasing literature on relationship of job satisfaction and job performance showed that job satisfaction is positively related to job performance. 2001). Work characteristics suggest that some people are inclined to be satisfied or dissatisfied with their job regardless of the nature of it or the organizational environment. Mirvis & Lawler (2015) concluded by their findings on the effect of job satisfaction on performance among bank tellers in terms of cash shortages that, satisfied workers are less likely to shown shortages and less likely to quit their jobs.

Lawler & Porter (2017) suggest that satisfaction affects employee effort. They explained that increased satisfaction from performance possibility helps to increase expectations of performance leading to reward. Satisfaction and productivity have critical links to affect each other. Efforts leads to effective performance which eventually leads to satisfaction but the kind of reward system under which employees operate ultimately affects satisfaction and performance (David, Joseph & Williams, 2016). Curall, Towler & Judge (2005) also found that the output and productivity of an organization is evaluated against the performance of its employees and therefore, better performance of employees demands high level of job satisfaction (Sousa-Posa & Sousa-Posa, 2000). Bakotić (2016) after examining employees performance indicators at the hiring stage found that employee's level of satisfaction and motivation affects their level of performance. In line with this argument, Jain (2016) confirmed that low level of job satisfaction negatively affects employee's commitment which eventually hinders achievement of organizational objectives and performance. Therefore, to retain higher performers require attractive packages and today's competitive world demands that organizations maintain higher performance to stay competitive in the market (Frye, 2004).

Conceptual Framework

Job satisfaction and its impact on job performance referring to the above literature review; the following conceptual research model is established to accomplish the research objectives, as It also describes the components of job satisfaction, including the nature of the job, compensation and benefits, growth opportunities, working conditions, relationship with co-workers, relationship with supervisors and promotion. This conceptual framework demonstrates how to motivate satisfied employees to do more work to improve performance.

Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis Development

Impact of compensation and benefit on job satisfaction and performance

Job satisfaction is the product of multiple factors such as salary, advancement, the work itself, supervision, co-worker relationships and promotion opportunities (Opkara, 2002). Pay is a very significant aspect, of these variables. Frye (2004) found that the association between equity-based compensation and success had been positive. It was further concluded that compensation plays a critical part in recruiting and retaining expert workers in a human capital-intensive business. In addition, the pay has a major effect on the degree of employee work satisfaction. Flexible compensation has also been shown to have little effect on work satisfaction levels (Igalens and Roussel, 1999). The study on the level of work satisfaction of managers in the public sector was conducted, and it was concluded that income is the key determinants of job satisfaction (Sokoya, 2000). The research into the relationship between work satisfaction and pay was conducted, and it was also found that the pay affects job satisfaction (Nguyen et al., 2003). Brudney and Coundry (2003) explained various variables which affect the performance of the organization's employees. They included such as salary, corporate engagement, pay-performance relationships, etc. There has been some empirical evidence that the link positive between compensation and performance is positive (Gneezy and Rustichini, 2000; Gardner et al., 2004; Tessema and Soeters, 2006). From the literature review, the research establishes that

H1: Compensation and benefit has positive effect on job satisfaction and employee performance

Impact of promotion on job satisfaction and employee performance

In their findings the researcher found the effect of various work satisfaction determinants. Several research concentrate on the demographic factors while others attribute job satisfaction to work environment. Other factors, such as equal system of promotion, work autonomy In evaluating the impact of work satisfaction, leadership behaviour, social interactions are also dominant (Dawson, 1987). (Nguyen et al., 2003) concluded that job satisfaction is the result of organizational promotion opportunities. Teseema and Soeters (2006) concluded that the relationship between promotional activities and perceived employee performance exists positive. If companies want to improve employee performance within the company, then workers should be granted equal promotional opportunities (Park et al., 2003). We formulate the hypothesis on the basis of the previous studies conducted.

H2: Promotion has positive impact on job satisfaction and employee performance.

Impact of job safety and security on job satisfaction and performance

Various researchers have conducted studies and found that work dissatisfaction is the product of employee discontent (Ashford et al., 2019; Davy et al., 2011). Significant factors such as poor job stability, working conditions and quality of employment, low salaries and lack of promotion, low job autonomy adversely affect the degree of employee satisfaction (Guest, 2004; Silla et al, 2005). During the study of Japanese employees, Abegglen (2018) found that employment conditions such as lifelong employment and the seniority scheme contribute to high commitment to job security. Bolt (2013), Mooney (2014), Rosow and Zager (2015) concluded that work efficiency is declining because of job insecurity. Iverson (2016) argued that workplace safety has a direct effect on organizational participation. Morris et al. (2013) came to the same conclusion. Research on job insecurity has been performed and work performance and organizational engagement have been found to be negatively associated with job insecurity (Rosenblatt and Ruvio, 2006). In the light of this, the study assumes that,

H3: Job safety and security has positive impact on job satisfaction and employee performance.

Impact of working conditions on job satisfaction and performance.

The researcher found that work environment is a major determinant of employee satisfaction at work (Spector, 2008). In the new study, the work climate was found to be better determinant for the scholars' job satisfactions (Reiner and Zhao, 2015; Carlan, 2007; Ellickson and Logsdon, 2001; Forsyth and Copes, 2014).

In addition, there is variance in terms of the workers ' compensation packages, working conditions, rewards, recognition and fringe benefits (Lavy, 2007). Factors such as lack of promotion, working conditions, low job security and low degree of autonomy have adversely affected worker satisfaction. Guest (2004), Silla et al., (2005) and (Ceylan, 1998) concluded that the terms of employment have an effect on employee satisfaction. This include adequate work and office rooms, temperature, lighting, ventilation and so on. It supports the hypothesis of:

H4: Working conditions have positive impact on job satisfaction and employee performance.

Impact of relationship with co-workers on job satisfaction and performance

The scholars previous found that environmental factors are important determinant of job satisfaction. The level of salary, promotion, appraisal system, climate management, and relation with co-workers are the vital factors. (Lambert et al., 2001). James (2016) concluded that the working as a team has significant impact on the satisfaction level of employees as it affects their performance. It is essential to recognize to the significance of these factors to boost the satisfaction level in the workforce. The researchers found factors

such as pay, promotion and employee satisfaction affecting the employee's sense of job satisfaction (Schermerhorn et al., 2005). Padilla-Velez (2013) argued that the performance could be improved and with the aid of socialization and contact between workers, absenteeism can be minimized. Thus, on the basis of earlier studies we propose the

H5: Relationship with co-workers has positive impact on job satisfaction and employee performance.

Impact of relationship with supervisors on job satisfaction and performance

Brunetto and Farr-Wharton (2002) concluded that supervising the immediate manager raises the level of work satisfaction among workers in the public sector. With managerial behaviour and supervision, the efficiency and output of subordinates can be enhanced. The supervisors' appreciation of the accomplishments leads to job satisfaction and is helpful in tackling the issue. Okpara (2004) conducted the IT managers study and found that with the aid of supervision job satisfaction among managers can be increased.

It was found differently that social relationship, relationship of boss, has little effect on workplace job satisfaction (Brown and McIntosh, 2003). It has also been found that job satisfaction is not the product of supervisor satisfaction (Roelen et al., 2008). The supervisors' appreciation of the subordinate accomplishment increases their level of job satisfaction and is also useful for solving day-to-day problems. The productivity and performance of the subordinates is significant toward the managerial actions and supervision of the workers (Yen and McKinney, 2012). In view of said literature, the research proposes the hypothesis:

H6: Relationship with supervisors has positive impact on job satisfaction and employee performance.

Impact of nature of work on job satisfaction and performance

The scholars have found that the job satisfaction has had a major impact on various variables. Those considerations are like salary, prospects for advancement, clarification of tasks and contact with colleagues and supervisors. Ting (2017) and Locke (2015) researched that the work itself had a strong connection with the happiness of the workers. Robbins et al (2003) refer to the work itself as "the degree to which the job provides stimulating jobs, learning opportunities for the worker and personal development, and the ability to be responsible and accountable for the results." Employees want work that fit the skills, which are mentally challenging (Robbins, 2013). Hence, the literature supports the hypothesis:

H7: The nature of work has positive impact on job satisfaction and employee performance

Data and Methods

For the purpose of this research explanatory, and descriptive research were used. Thus, descriptive research design was deemed to be the most appropriate method for this research. However, the research also used quantitative research design. Quantitative research design enables the research to collect, group and categorize data to allow for statistical analysis. The population consisted all the Three (3) teaching Hospitals in Ghana namely Komfo-Anokye teaching hospital, Korle-Bu teaching hospital, Tamale teaching hospital with employees including Doctors, nurses, health assistant, Pharmacists. It is worthy to note that, all the targeted respondents are involved in the hospital and are current employees. In this research, two hundred and fifty (300) respondents were purposively chosen from the three (3) Teaching Hospital in Ghana from the period of 2017- 2020 for the analysis. However, for the inclusion of the sample, the following restrictions were imposed, only sampled hospitals are selected. In complete questionnaires from respondents with other missing relevant data were excluded from the research.

Questionnaires

The research conducted a pilot and pretesting of the questionnaire by deploying it experts of health in Ghana. The questionnaires were given to the experts from the Ministry of Health, Ghana Health Service and retired medical Practitioners known by the authors. They were asked to review, correct and endorse for improvements and amendments of the original draft work of the questionnaire for its implication, content as well as the wordings. The selected Teaching Hospital are displayed in appendix. The revised and modified questionnaires were deployed to the targeted respondents. The questionnaires were into three folds. The first fold asked the respondents on their profile. The remaining section addressed and asked questions on factors that contribute significantly to job satisfaction among employees of Ghana health service and their effect on performance of employees. However, the confidentiality of the responses was assured, hence increase the response rate.

Model Specifications

To examine the effects of determinates of Job Satisfaction on the performance of employees of Health Service in Ghana, the study estimate regressions of factors or determinants influences on job Satisfaction and employee performance. This Eq. (1) and (2) using multiple regressions as follows;

$$JS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NOFJB_1 + \beta_2 CPBNTs_2 + \beta_3 JSTY_3 + \beta_4 WCN_4 + \beta_5 RCW_5 + \beta_6 RES_6 + \beta_7 PMT_7 + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ Eq.1}$$

$$EP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NOFJB_1 + \beta_2 CPBNTs_2 + \beta_3 GOPP_3 + \beta_4 WCN_4 + \beta_5 RCW_5 + \beta_6 RES_6 + \beta_7 PMT_7 + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ Eq.2}$$

Where JB is job Satisfaction, EP is Employee Performance, NOFJB is the nature of the job, CPBNT is compensation and benefits, JSTY is the Job Safety and Security, WCN is working conditions, RCW is relationship with co-workers, RES is relationship with supervisors and PMT is promotion. β_0 Indicate the constant parameter of the regression model. ($\beta_1 - \beta_4$) represent the coefficients of the independent variables on the dependent variable and ε_{it} is the stochastic or error term.

To test Hypothesis 1-7, the research measured Job Satisfaction and employee Performance as respondent rate the effect of the determinants of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Hospitals. Bowling et al 2015; Loan, 2020; King, 2017; TE used this approach when examining the influence of job satisfaction on the performance of employees. However, the research follows the literature such as Robert et al 2020; Adeyemo's (2010) by measuring employee performance as respondents rating Job Satisfaction factors impact on their performance at Hospitals respectively.

Independent Variables

To examine the effects of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance on of Ghana Health Service, the research used determinants or factors associated with Job Satisfaction in line with the literature (Loan, 2020; King, 2017;). They are nature of the job, compensation and benefits, Job security and Safety, Working Conditions, Relationship with Co-Workers, Relationship with Supervisors and Promotion. They are signified by the effects they posed on Employee Performance. This effect stems from determinants indicators in Job Satisfaction literature. ((Torlak & Kuzey, C. 2019; (Alamdard et al., 2012).). They were measured as respondent were asked about the effects of determinants on their Employee Performance with aid of Likert Scale ranges from (1) strongly disagree to strongly agree (5).

Data Analysis

The study processed the data obtained and analysed using a statistical package for social science (SPSS). The research maintained that, no pinpointing information data was obtained, and only summary results were reported. Regression model was utilized to ascertain the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable.

Results and Findings

This sections provides the findings of the study based on the data obtained from respondents.

Determinants contribute to Job Satisfaction

Employees were asked on their perception of the best determinants that contributes significantly to the satisfaction at their respective hospitals. They were asked to rate: the nature of the job, compensation and benefits, Job safety and security, working conditions, Relationship with co-workers, Relationship with supervisors and promotion on the Likert scale from 1 (Strongly agree) to 4 (Strongly disagree).

Table 6 Determinants to Job Satisfaction

Determinants to Job Satisfaction	Frequency	Your level of agreement	
		Mean	SD
Nature of the Job	80	5.2 (1)	1.145
Working conditions	79	4.6 (3)	.2209
Job safety and Security	38	4.9 (2)	.5929
Compensation and benefits	74	3.3 (6)	.6889
Relationship with Co-Workers	30	4.1 (4)	.0009
Relation with Supervisors	27	3.9 (5)	.0529
Promotion	62	2.9 (7)	1.5129

Majority of the respondents rated "nature of the Job" as the most determinants to Job Satisfaction of Ghana Health Service. It is evidence by (N=80, M=5.2, Sd=1.145). Respondent supported their argument with the fact that, employees are most satisfied when they find their work interesting, according to an article in Human Resource Management. Being able to retain a certain amount of autonomy allows workers to develop their own challenges and find ways to overcome obstacles, leading to a more satisfying work experience.

Meanwhile, "Job Safety and Security" was seen as the next determinants to Job Satisfaction of employees at the Teaching Hospitals of the Ghana Health Service. It had several 38 representing 15.2% of the total respondents. In addition, working conditions was seen as another determinants affecting employees Job Satisfaction. In fact, it had a mean rating of (4.6). The least factor or determinant to Job Satisfaction according to the participants is "promotion". It had a mean rating of (2.9), and SD (1.559). The table below displays a summary of the findings.

Empirical Findings

This section provides the results of empirical studies relating to the effects of the determinants to Job satisfaction on Employee Performance of selected Teaching Hospitals under the Ghana Health Service using statistical regression model.

However, before evaluating the conceptual relationships of the model, an evaluation of the internal consistency and reliability of the measurement scale was conducted. To test the internal consistency or reliability of the measurement of the study variables, Cronbach alpha was utilized. The table below shows the reliability test of the independent and dependent variables.

Table 2 Reliability Test and Variable description

	Abbreviation	Factor Name	Composite Reliability	References
Job Satisfaction determinants				
	NTJ	Nature of the Job	0.780	Alamdar et al., 2012); Torlak & Kuzey, (2017)
	CBNT	Compensation, and Benefits	0.825	
	JSTY	Job Safety and Security	0.712	
	WCD	Working Conditions	0.813	
	RWW	Relationship with Co Workers	0.812	Robert et al 2020;

	RWS	Relationship with supervisors	0.833	Adeyemo's (2010)
	PMT	Promotion	0.723	
	EP	Employee Performance		Robert et al 2020; Adeyemo's (2010)
Employee Performance			0.811	

Based on the table shown above, Cronbach Alpha was used and all variables were above the threshold level (0.70) which is the accepted rate for study (Nunnally, 1978) as cited in Osei Mandell et al (2018). Therefore, these findings are visible in the research.

Summary Statistics

The table below shows the summary statistics of the variables used in the research. On average, employee performance increased through the various facets of Job satisfaction with a percentage of 35 percent. It emanates from a range of (14.39) that stems from a minimum of (0.24) for employee performance and a maximum of (14.63). The positive sign of both maximum and minimum values shows the increasing of employee performance in Hospitals. On average, employee performance of selected Hospitals improves through nature of the Job of 46 percent. However, the mean value of compensation and benefits was (3.36) with a minimum value of (2.51) and maximum value of (5.2). Employee Performance escalates as results of relationship with workers with a mean value of 4.2 with a minimum value of (3.22) and maximum value 4.81 respectively. The average value for promotion as a facet improving employee performance was (1.07), Job Safety and Security (3.6), and working conditions (3.38). The summary of the findings are as follows;

Table 2 Descriptive Summary

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
EP	3.58	4.61	0.24	14.63
NOFJB	4.60	0.90	2.73	5.56
CPBNT	3.36	0.82	2.51	5.2
JSTY	3.56	0.65	2.52	4.54
WCN	3.38	0.65	2.12	4.61
RCW	4.20	0.58	3.22	4.81
RES	5.11	0.94	3.13	5.85
PMT	1.07	0.49	0.59	2.19

Descriptive Analysis

The study presents the empirical findings regarding the effects of Job Satisfaction (nature of the job, promotion, compensation and benefits, working conditions, relationship with supervisors, with workers) on employee performance of Teaching Hospitals in Ghana. In model (2), which is the multiple regression involving effect of the determinants to Job Satisfaction on employee performance. The correlation table, there is positive relationship between the facets and employee performance. In looking at the correlation coefficients between the variables, it shows that, the signs are consistent with the literature and the study hypothesis since the magnitude coefficient is less than 9. Moreover, compensation and benefits and relationship with supervisors are positively and highly linked which approves that, it is one of the facets of Job satisfaction of which employee performance is increased or affected. Empirically, the results show that all the discussed facets or determinants of Job satisfaction affect organizations employee performance implying that, it influences employee's performance. The summary of the findings is provided below,

Table 3 Correlation of Variables for Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
EP	1							
NOFJB	.1474**	1						
CPBNT	.3651**	0.2721	1					
JSTY	.2223**	0.1293	0.0368	1				
WCN	.2143**	0.3068	0.3007	0.2202	1			
RCW	.1347**	0.5498	0.5440	0.3007	0.3436	1		
RES	.3280**	0.6094	0.3784	0.1563	0.4293	0.6249	1	
PMT	0.2378	0.2967	0.2183	0.3607	0.4301	0.0322	0.4589	1

Table 4 Analysis of the Regression model

Multiple R	R Square	Adjusted R-squared	Std. Error of Estimate	Prob > F
0.589	0.541	0.3725	1.45	0.4331

From the results shown above, all explanatory variables used in the research to assess the Job Satisfaction on employee performance explain 54% of organization performance (adjusted R- squared 0.541). Thus, Job Satisfaction facets or determinants (nature of the job, promotion, compensation and benefits, working conditions, relationship with supervisors, with workers) effects employee performance of Hospitals in Ghana, while other facets or determinants of Job Satisfaction not considered not in this research contributes the remaining 46% effecting Hospitals performance of employees. These findings provide support for Hypotheses that predict positive relationship between employee performance and Job Satisfaction determinants. The results authenticate or validate preceding empirical research conducted on the Job satisfaction on Employee Performance in Pakistan using structured questionnaires (Farman et al 2013).

Table 5 Regression equations for testing the mediation of Job satisfaction, and determinants of Job satisfaction, and Employee Performance

Eqn.	Dependent Variables	Independent Variables	Beta	t-statistics	R-square	F- Value
1a	Job Satisfaction	Compensation and benefits	0.250	3.639	0.063	13.243
1b		Promotion	0.236	3.424	0.056	1.726
1c		Job safety and security	0.116	1.637	0.013	2.677
1d		Working conditions	0.288	4.238	0.083	17.962
1e		Relationship with CO-workers	0.211	3.036	0.044	9.219
1f		Relationship with Supervisor	0.123	1.739	0.015	3.024
1g		Nature of Work	0.243	3.527	0.059	12.443
2a	Employee Performance	Compensation and Benefits	0.057	0.799	0.003	0.639
2b		Promotion	0.064	0.898	0.004	0.807
2c		Job safety and security	0.090	1.273	0.008	1.621
2d		Working Conditions	0.121	1.722	0.015	2.964
2e		Relationship with Co-workers	0.148	2.106	0.022	4.436
2f		Relationship with supervisors	0.138	1.967	0.019	3.870
2g		Nature of work	0.073	1.028	0.005	1.058
3a	Employee Performance	Compensation and Benefits	0.031	0.426	0.013	1.294
		Job Satisfaction	0.102	1.395		
		Promotion				
3b		Job satisfaction	0.040	0.549	0.014	1.35
3c		Job Safety and security	0.100	1.378		
		Job satisfaction				
		Working Conditions	0.078	1.104	0.018	1.819
3d		Job satisfaction	0.101	1.418	0.21	2.098
3e		Relationship with Co-workers	0.866	1.330	0.030	3.040
		Job satisfaction	0.083	1.108	0.026	2.626
3f	Relationship with supervisors	0.135	1.906	0.016	1.566	
3g	Job satisfaction	0.091	1.277			
	Nature of work	0.121	1.677			
	Job satisfaction	0.084	1.173			
		0.070	0.847			
		0.102	1.438			

The research adopted the procedure of Judd and Kenny (1981) and Baron and Kenny (1986), for the mediation of factor, that is, job satisfaction in this research. The equations developed was used to the

findings. In the first equation, independent factors like compensation and benefits, promotion, working conditions, Job safety and security, relationship with co-workers, relationship with supervisor, nature of the work and mediating variable job satisfaction are regressed. The second equation involved the regression of independent variables with the dependent variable performance of the employee. However, the independent variables including the moderating variable are also regressed. The results regarding the effect of independent factors on the mediating variable “job satisfaction” and the effect of mediating variable on the dependent variable “employee performance” are shown in above. The research examined in the Equations, the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between facets of job satisfaction such as compensation and benefits, promotion, job safety and security, working conditions, relationship with co-workers, relationship with supervisor, nature of the work and the employee performance in the teaching Hospitals of the Ghana Health Service . From the findings, job satisfaction was regressed on facets of job satisfaction (mediator) and the results are found significant. In the second equation (2a), employee performance (dependent variable) was also regressed on the independent variables (predictor) and the results shows positive relationship. In the third equation (3a), the employee performance was regressed on the facets of job satisfaction and job satisfaction. In Equation 2a, beta (0.057) is less than that of Equations 1a (0.250); hence, the job satisfaction is the significant mediator and fulfill the conditions of mediation. In testing the mediating effect of job satisfaction and relationship of facets of job satisfaction and employee performance. The results evidenced the relationship between job satisfaction and facets of job satisfaction and employee performance. The relationship between job satisfaction and facets of job satisfaction was more significant as compared to employee performance as indicated in Equation 3a. The finding confirmed that job satisfaction is mediating in this model. Therefore, the results show that all determinants to job satisfaction are associated with employee performance since the coefficients are statistically significant. These findings provide support for Hypothesis 1-7 that predict the relationship positive relationship between job satisfaction determinants and employee performance. Taking only into account, the findings concerning the effects, it is found that, Job satisfaction is significantly related to employee performance of Hospitals in Ghana. These findings are consistent with those Morrison & Phelps (1999), and Stewart & Brown, (2019), Liu et al (2017). Concerning positive relationship between employee performance and the determinants of Job satisfaction, the hypothesis was accepted and confirmed, which is in line with other researchers examined the relationships and found similar results. (Audenaert et al 2019).

In addition, the findings also reveal a positive relationship between employee performance and benefits and compensation. The hypothesis was confirmed and accepted. Other scholars who have conducted with this factor variables found similar results. Compensation is one of the important factors for inducing and motivating the workers for higher efficiency and greater output. A compensation and benefits attract a worker’s attention and stimulates him to work. Besides wages and salaries, employees are paid incentives depending on the performance and paid as regulatory as wages and salaries. All the independent factor variables have a positive influence on employee's performance which is in line with other researcher's findings. Approaching the aforementioned results from managerial insightful, it can be said that, managers should pay attention to Job satisfaction facets since it can significantly affect employee's performance. Therefore, human resources practices should be enhanced continually in terms of employees' compensation and benefits, working conditions, growth opportunities, promotion, and relationship with supervisors. The mentality of every employee should be changed through seminars and workshops to empower them. Proper logistics should be provided as well as adequate budgetary allocation for the human resource department, to overcome improper keeping of records of staff and excess staff.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The Ghana Health Service is working to build a happy work force to run the organization's well-being. In fact, if an employee feels happy with the work, then an employee is motivated to put more effort into results. Employees of the hospitals of the Ghana Health Service can accomplish the requirements of job satisfaction by taking. There have been numerous strikes by Doctors, Nurses, Health Assistants in Ghana since they were dissatisfied with pay, promotion, working conditions, development policies, care given to doctors and many other factors. The study finds positive effect of determinants of Job Satisfaction Employee

performance. This implies that, employees' compensation and benefits, working conditions, Job safety and security, promotion, and relationship with supervisors, and workers are positively related with employee's performance and the effect is statistically significant. Therefore, management of Hospitals in Ghana should focus on these variables: employees' compensation and benefits, working conditions, Job Safety and security, promotion, and relationship with supervisors, and workers in order to enhance the level of employee satisfaction and to increase their level of performance. In addition, the government should consider all factors like promotion, working conditions, co-workers and nature of work which have significant impact on the job satisfaction level as proved in this study.

There are certain limitations that may have influence the empirical findings. Due to data availability, this current research could not use larger sample size and years. Therefore, further studies could examine using larger sample sizes. The study focused on only public owned hospitals, therefore generalization could not be applied to all Hospitals in Ghana, so further studies could examine by comparing both public and private hospitals on how job satisfaction improve their level of performance.

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